

Determining Satisfaction and Behavioral Intentions of WEBCON Participants Amidst Covid-19 Pandemic in Davao City, Philippines

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Abstract: *The study aimed to investigate and determine the satisfaction and behavioral intentions of Webcon participants. This study employed a descriptive-correlational method utilizing the descriptive survey method technique as the data collection instrument. The statistical tools used were mean ANOVA and T-test. An online survey through Google forms was used to distribute the survey questionnaires to the randomly selected delegate participants of Digital Web WEBCON in Davao City. Using ANOVA and T-test, the study results show that the satisfaction and behavioral intention of Webcon participants regarding age, sex, civil status, and educational attainment have no significant difference except in terms of webinars attended. Moreover, using average weighted mean, there is a manifestation of the high level of satisfaction, particularly in terms of attendee's reactions and experience, and a high level of behavioral intention such as that they will recommend it to other people to attend the Webinar. The results imply that Webcon organizers that focus on the essential elements such as webinar setup and content to obtain virtual attention, participation, and experience can attain virtual participants' satisfaction and influences their behavioral intention to participate in future webinars.*

Keywords: Webinar, Satisfaction, Behavioral Intention, Webcon participants, Davao City, Philippines

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent competition among convention destinations and venues has highlighted the need for a better understanding of the convention or conference attendee behavior, including their decision-making process and evaluation of the convention experience (Severt, 2017). Because of Covid-19, most conventions nowadays are conducted through a webinar. However, in the Webinar, every presenter who uses technology during a presentation runs the risk of technical difficulties interfering with their time at the podium. During a webinar, in which the audience views an audiovisual production on their computers, opportunities for technical problems are virtually limitless. Participants might become annoyed and frustrated with these issues and may disconnect from the online meeting, literally or mentally (Lindblad, 2020).

Moreover, Malle and Knobe (2017) emphasized the importance of behavioral intention, who observes that intention is the element that links desire and belief to action. They argued that an intentional effort required to fulfill the desired state influences the perception that a course of action will satisfy the hunger. Consequently, researchers are in a position to predict the use of new technologies by using Davis (2009) proposal of the successive relationship of belief, attitude, intention, and behavior in the Technology Assistance Model (TAM), such as in the case of Webinar nowadays due to Covid-19. Perceived usefulness is the degree to which a person believes that the utilization of a system will result in the enhancement of their job performance, while perceived ease of use is the extent to which a person conceives that utilizing a system will require less physical and mental effort (Liao & Lu, 2018).

The relationship between satisfaction and behavioral intention was reflected in the study of Mittal, Kumar, and Tsiros (2015), who found a close relationship between the two variables. Behavioral intention is composed of word-of-mouth behavior and intent to return. The importance of satisfaction related to the attendee's future decision-making has been confirmed by Swan and Combs (2016), citing satisfaction as a post-purchase attitude that affects cognitive and affective aspects in pre-purchase, purchase, and post-purchase phases of buying goods and receiving services. Word-of-mouth communication has been proven to be one of the strongest predictors for shaping the behaviors and attitudes of future clientele (Gremler, 2014).

The scarcity of related studies and literature on behavioral intention on webinars and its relationship to participants' satisfaction has created a research gap among local researchers. Thus this study was conducted to fill up the gap. With the digital WEBCon event in Davao City, the researchers find it relevant to conduct a study regarding the level of satisfaction and behavioral intention, as perceived by WEBCon delegates or participants. This study is essential as this can be utilized as the basis for future enhancement plans or programs in the tourism sector.

This study aimed to determine the satisfaction and behavioral intentions of Webcon participants. Moreover, this study was guided by the following objectives: To measure the level of satisfaction of Webcon participants in terms of experience, and attendees/ trainee reactions; To assess the level of the behavioral intention of Webcon participants.

The Webinar is a live online seminar where the participating viewers with an Internet connection may ask questions and comment via a computer, tablet PC, or mobile phone. The word "webinar" derives from the words "web" and "seminar" and was established in the late '90s. Webinars may be used for educational purposes such as presentations or workshops, but they work great for business conferences. It is a live interaction between the participants, but the seminar can be recorded, allowing it to be watched later if needed. The Webinar includes transmitting voice audio, PowerPoint presentation, written messages, and multimedia between the participants (Careless 2012). Similarly, webinars are seminars that are performed on the World Wide Web. They can be meetings, conferences, demonstrations, training or teaching, or events designed to give information either one-way or interactively. Webinars can include video, audio and textual communication. Once the user has installed the software, they will be invited to join a meeting at an allotted time. The participant users also need a pair of headphones and a microphone. Once entered, the participant will find themselves in a virtual classroom or meeting room.

In addition, webinars are in a rapid growth stage, both in capability and in usage. Companies have realized that the education they provide to their employees in the globalized world saves enormous time and creates savings if it is done with the help of modern technology. Online technology makes an opportunity to join seminars from anywhere on earth with an Internet connection, saving money in travel expenses. Travelling takes time, and the time of an employer is money (Newman 2013). Moreover, the most popular way to use webinars is lecturing, where the Lecturer's voice audio is shared one way to the participants. However, it is possible to interact with the other participants by using voice audio to ask questions through a microphone or to write the questions and comments in a chat window in an open conversation that the other participants may see and comment too. It is even possible to utilize social media services with a chatting feature during the Webinar, which allows the conversation to continue after it has ended. Moving from one place to another requires effort and possibly lowers the attendance rate, and in webinar lectures, this problem does not occur (Huhmarkangas, 2014).

Satisfaction is a customer's judgment of perceived outcome in contrast to expectations. If the experience does not correspond to the expectations, the customer is dissatisfied. If the background checks to expectations, the customer is satisfied, and when the experience exceeds expectations, the customer is delighted. (Kotler & Keller 2019). Customers set their expectations towards a service differently, and therefore satisfaction levels may differ a lot among the same service experience. Expectations are selected based on the customer's loyalty relationship towards the brand, earlier experiences, and the price of the service.

Behavioral intentions can be expressed as comparing behavior, price sensitivity, repurchase, and sharing of information. Customer satisfaction guides good behavioral intentions, and customer dissatisfaction leads to unfavorable intentions (Olorunniwo, 2016). Behavioral intentions are seen as post-purchase as the extent of satisfaction and post-purchase action. Post-purchase experiences of a product or service affect customers' behavioral intentions (Spiteri & Dion, 2014).

Moreover, customers show a high tendency to repurchase the product if they are satisfied. Customers may return the product if they are dissatisfied. They may complain to the company, take legal action against it, or decide to stop buying the product and warn other people (Kotler & Keller, 2019). So, it is essential to get good behavioral intentions from

customers, and for this reason, companies should truthfully represent the product's likely performance (Wu & Liang, 2019).

II. METHODOLOGY

The researchers made use of quantitative research using descriptive-correlational methods. It is a statistical measure of a relationship between two or more variables and indicates how one variable may predict another. The descriptive techniques discussed above permit a statement, in the form of correlations, about that relationship. More specifically, the correlational research design is a non-experimental study in which relationships are assessed without manipulating independent variables or randomly assigning participants to different conditions. Therefore, this will be an appropriate research design employed for the study and will try to determine the relationship between satisfaction and behavioral intention of Digital Web WEBCON in Davao City.

The respondents of this study were randomly selected 500 delegates/participants of Digital Web WEBCON in Davao City. The researchers used simple random sampling. Simple random sampling is the purest and the most straightforward probability sampling strategy. It is also the most popular method for choosing a sample among the population for a wide range of purposes wherein each member of the population is equally likely to be chosen as part of the sample.

Table 1. Profile of the respondents

Profile Variables	Group	Frequency	Percent
Attended a webinar in the past six months	Yes	346	69.2%
	No	154	30.8%
Sex	Male	192	38.4%
	Female	308	61.6%
Age	19 below	51	10.2%
	20-29	356	71.2%
	30-39	77	15.4%
	40-59	16	3.2%
	60 above	0	0.0%
Civil Status	Single	453	90.6%
	Married	45	9.0%
	Separated/Widowed	2	.4%
Educational Attainment	Elementary Level	2	.4%
	Elementary Graduate	15	3.0%
	High School Level	23	4.6%
	High School Graduate	247	49.4%
	College Graduate	213	42.6%

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents. In terms of webinars attended, 346 respondents, or 69 percent, have attended webinars in the past six months. In terms of sex, the majority are female respondents, with 308 or 61.6 percent. In terms of age, most respondents belong to the 20-29 years old bracket, comprising 71.2 percent, while others belong to 19 years old-below, 30-39- and 40-59-year-old brackets. With regards to civil status, most respondents are single, with 453, or 90.6 percent. In terms of educational attainment, the majority are high school graduates and college graduates, with 247 (49.4 percent) and 213 (42.6 percent), respectively.

The researcher used an adapted questionnaire from Gegenfurtner, Zitt, and Ebner (2020) for the effect of the Webinar, which was modified to suit the context of the study and was presented to the panel of experts for validation. The effect of Webinar includes the following indicators: experience and attendees/ trainee reaction.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the level of satisfaction of Webcon participants with an overall mean of 3.97 or a high level. This table illustrates that the respondents have high observed satisfaction with their experience and reactions to participating in and attending a Webcon. The level of satisfaction of webcon participants in terms of their experience has a weighted

mean of 3.91. In contrast, attendees and trainees' reaction has collected a weighted mean of 4.03 towards participating and attending a Webcon.

The high level of satisfaction of Webcon participants is supported by the study of Myers &Schiltz (2012), where it questioned the undergraduate students' learning and attitudes after using a webinar platform in the United States of America. The study shows that participants' grades were higher compared to online and on-site classes, and their attitudes regarding the class improved. This indicates that the inclusion of satisfaction as an outcome since user satisfaction has always been recognized as a critical gauge of information system success. (DeLone& McLean, 1992).

Specifically, in terms of experience as a factor to the satisfaction of Webcon participants, several pieces of literature have looked into various experiences of webinar users. For example, the Illinois Library Association launched webinars using Elluminate software for employee training. The majority of participants appreciated the webinar experience and agreed that webinars were an excellent tool for professional development (Wang & Hsu, 2008). Similarly, in terms of reactions as a factor of satisfaction of Webcon participants, in the study of Stein, Shibata, Bautista, &Tokuda (2010), it indicates that the students enrolled in this graduate-level course at a Northeastern University in the United States of America (USA) have enjoyed and appreciated the tools that the Webinar offered such as whiteboards and polls. Students were also pleased with the robust and engaged discourse that took place due to synchronous communication. The findings above implied that it is essential for any events, including Webcon, to determine or know the experiences and the reactions of participants or attendees to know if they are satisfied or there are still aspects that need to be improved to attain participants' satisfaction. Moreover, this also implied that attendees' or participants' satisfaction would result in future participation.

Table 2. Level of Satisfaction of Webcon Participants

Indicators	Mean	Std. Dev.	Descriptive Level
Experience	3.91	0.742	High
Attendees and Trainee Reactions	4.03	0.758	High
Overall	3.97	0.696	High

Table 3 shows the level of the behavioral intention of Webcon participants with an overall mean of 4.02 or a high level. This means that the behavioral intention of Webcon participants is often manifested through their desire to participate actively in the Webinar. This was supported by Lindblad (2020) that because of Covid-19, most conventions nowadays are conducted through webinars. This was also stated by Gegenfurtner and Ebner (2019) that webinars had gained increasing popularity in recent years primarily because webinars provide synchronous online contexts that trainees can access internet connectivity ubiquitously from anywhere.

Specifically, it shows that the highest-rated statement is that they will encourage other people to attend webinar convention/conference, with a mean of 4.06, which was followed by the statement that in the future, they intend to attend the webinar convention/conference and say positive things about the webinar convention/conference to other people, with an identical means of 4.03, described as High. On the other hand, the lowest-rated statement is that they will recommend webinar conventions/conferences to other people, with a mean of 3.95, described as High. This means that Webinar is an effective tool in conducting conventions or conferences and that intention of participants to join or participate is on a high level. This implied that through Webinar, it increases the behavioral intention of participants for it creates connectivity and convenience for them, and this was corroborated by Newman (2013) that online technology creates an opportunity to join the seminars from anywhere on earth with an Internet connection, saving money in travel expenses. This also implied that Webinar is an important tool in seminars, training, conferences and conventions, as the world is experiencing limited mobility due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Moreover, findings also implied that Webinar is an alternative mechanism, which is also effective and feasible during the pandemic. The intention of the participants solely rests on their experiences and satisfaction during the said event.

Table 3. Level of Behavioral Intention of Webcon Participants

Items	Mean	Std. Dev.	Descriptive Level
1. I will recommend webinar conventions/conferences to other people.	3.95	0.944	High

2. I will say positive things about the webinar convention/conference to other people.	4.03	0.866	High
3. I will encourage other people to attend webinar convention/conference	4.06	0.872	High
4. In the future, I intend to attend the webinar convention/conference.	4.03	0.883	High
Overall	4.02	0.813	High

Table 4 demonstrates the significant difference in determining satisfaction of Webcon participants when analyzed according to the attended Webinar of the respondents. Regarding the attended Webinar, the overall p-result of 0.000 shows a significant difference in determining the satisfaction and behavioral intention of Webcon participants. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction when analyzed by attended Webinars. This implied that participants had varied satisfaction levels depending on the attended Webinar and the attended Webinar is a determinant or a factor that affects their satisfaction level.

This result is supported by the study of Perez et al. (2019), stating that satisfaction is a positive attitude from the learning participants towards the process that occurs in the learning activity. Furthermore, webinars have been used by Kanter et al. (2013) to model and train therapy scenarios. According to Kanter (2013), participants have shown positive attitudes with the facilitators and peer trainees' synchronous engagement, input, and help. Findings are also supported by Richardson (2018) and Michael (2013) that active participation in educational activities such as webinars is essential for learning since active participation improves students' level of understanding, the ability to process material, and the retention of knowledge (Wilke, 2013).

On the other hand, regarding sex, the overall p-result of 0.375 shows that there is no significant difference existed in determining the satisfaction of Webcon participants. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that sex does not show any significant difference in determining Webcon participants' satisfaction in attending and joining Webcon. This implied that sex is not a factor or determinant in creating differences in the level of satisfaction of Webcon Participants.

Findings are contrary to Joshanloo's (2015) statement that women reported higher levels of satisfaction than men, while Jovanovic (2015) stressed that gender differences in satisfaction were found to be significant yet small. This was also the same view of Geerling and Diener (2019) that women were more satisfied than men, while Zou (2018) that life satisfaction varies significantly across men and women.

Similarly, regarding age, the overall result of 0.480, which is greater than the .05 level of significance, proves that there is no significant difference in determining the satisfaction of Webcon participants, thus failing to reject the null hypothesis of the study. The finding shows that age does not indicate any significant difference in determining Webcon participants' satisfaction in attending and joining Webcon. This implies that age is not a part of determining the satisfaction and behavioral intention of Webcon participants.

Findings were supported by the survey-based study conducted by Gupta and Sengupta (2021). Age is independent of the other factors under the study "Webinar as the Future Educational Tool in Higher Education of India" except its inclusion in distance mode of education. Among the students participating in the survey, in general, the higher the age, the higher is the class in which they are enrolled. The students enrolled in higher classes may understand that the number of seats for higher education is limited, and they have to join a job to secure their future. Moreover, the findings were in contrast to the study of Riza (2017), who hypothesized that as people get older, they gain more satisfaction. This was also the view of Liu (2018) that as people grew older, they became increasingly satisfied with their life. However, this was in line with the study of Inglehart (2010), who found almost no differences across age groups in the percentage of people who indicated that they were satisfied.

Likewise, in terms of civil status, findings revealed a result of the p-value of 0.915, which is greater than the .05 level of significance, showing that respondents' civil status has no significant difference in determining Webcon participants' satisfaction in joining a Webcon. This implied that civil status is not a part of determining the satisfaction and behavioral intention of Webcon participants.

Findings were in contrast to the statement of Botha and Booysen (2015) that satisfaction is significantly higher for married compared to widowed individuals, while the former are more satisfied than those from all other marital statuses (Coombs, 2016). This was also stated by Hinks and Gruen (2017) that married people are more satisfied compared to those from all other marital status groups. Frey (2015) added that married men are not significantly more satisfied than men from other marital statuses as a whole; marriage is positively associated with satisfaction among women but not among men (Ferris, 2017).

Also, regarding educational attainment, the result of the p-value of 0.772 of satisfaction from between and within groups respondents entails that there is no significant difference in determining the participants' satisfaction in attending a Webcon. Findings implied that educational attainment is a nonfactor or non-determinant in creating differences in the satisfaction level of Webcon participants.

Findings contrast to the study of Wilson (2017), which shows a positive, strong correlation between education attainment and satisfaction. Similar conclusions are met by Di Tella (2012), who used psychological data from Europe and the United States to prove that higher education positively affects self-reported satisfaction. Frey and Stutzer (2012) also obtain a positive correlation, even after considering factors that are considered a channel through which education may influence satisfaction. Recent work by Blanchflower (2018) also shows that satisfaction is higher for the more educated.

Table 4. Independent samples *t*-test results showing the differences in determining satisfaction of Webcon participants when analyzed by Profile.

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	t-value	p-value	Decision on Ho
	154	3.89	0.851			
Attended Webinar	346	4.06	0.663	4.246	0.000*	Reject
	154	3.78	0.729			
Sex	Male	192	0.760	0.888	0.375	Accept
	Female	308	0.653			
Age	Between Groups	3	0.400	0.825	0.480	
	Within Groups	496	0.485			Accept
	Total	499				
Civil Status	Between Groups	2	0.043	.088	.915	
	Within Groups	497	0.487			Accept
	Total	499				
Educational Attainment	Between Groups	4	.219	.451	.772	
	Within Groups	495	.487			Accept
	Total	499				

Table 5 demonstrates the significant difference in determining the behavioral intention of Webcon participants when analyzed according to the Profile of the respondents. Regarding the attended Webinar, the overall p-result of 0.018 shows a significant difference in determining the behavioral intention of Webcon participants. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means a significant difference in the level of behavioral intention when analyzed by attended Webinars. Participants have varied behavioral intentions depending on the attended Webinar and that the attended Webinar is a factor or determinant. Findings are supported by Thrustone (2011), Liker (2010), and Ajzen and Fishbein (1990) that behavioral intention is a single dimension of effect that a person feels for or against an object or an event. This was also stated by Perry (2011) that behavioral intention is usually affective states. These evaluations can be based on behavioral,

cognitive, and affective information and experiences. They are capable of guiding behavioral, cognitive, and affective responses.

Regarding sex, the overall p-result of 0.871 shows that no significant difference existed in determining the behavioral intention of Webcon participants. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that sex does not show any significant difference in determining Webcon participants' behavioral intention in attending and joining Webcon. This implied that sex is not a factor or determinant in creating differences in the level of the behavioral intention of Webcon Participants.

Findings are contrary to the study of Ramli (2012) that every individual's behavioral intention is different due to the effects of certain factors, one of which is gender. Fakhrudin (2014) stated that in psychological research, gender had been found to affect mindset, attitude, and belief in making decisions, impacting the readiness to perform a behavior. However, another study mentions that gender does not affect an individual's behavioral intention (Karyanto, 2015).

Likewise, regarding age, the overall p-result of 0.385 shows that no significant difference existed in determining the behavioral intention of Webcon participants. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that age does not show any significant difference in determining Webcon participants' behavioral intention in attending and joining Webcon. This implied that age is not a factor or determinant in creating differences in the level of the behavioral intention of Webcon Participants.

Findings are supported by Soto (2011) that as age seems to display a moderating role in technology acceptance models, they seem potential moderators on the relationship between personality and behavioral intention. Indeed, age differences in the big-five dimensions of personality have already been reported. For example, older adults were more agreeable than younger adults (Chapman et al., 2008).

Similarly, with regards to civil status, the overall p-result of 0.952 shows that no significant difference existed in determining the behavioral intention of Webcon participants. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that civil status does not show any significant difference in determining Webcon participants' behavioral intention in attending and joining Webcon. This implied that civil status is not a factor or determinant in creating differences in the level of the behavioral intention of Webcon Participants.

Findings are supported by Shalini (2016) that marital status is an important demographic variable, but there is a difference of opinion among researchers on whether it influences behavioral intention or not. Gong (2016) states that demographic factors like age, income, education, marital status, and perceived usefulness are significant predictors of behavioral intention. In contrast, Wongsiriwat (2017) indicates that marital status precisely does not influence behavioral intention parameters.

In addition, in terms of educational attainment, the overall p-result of 0.837 shows that no significant difference existed in determining the behavioral intention of Webcon participants. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that educational attainment does not significantly determine Webcon participants' behavioral intention to attend and join Webcon. This implied that educational attainment is not a factor or determinant in creating differences in the level of the behavioral intention of Webcon Participants. Findings are contrary to the study of Carpenter and Fleishman (2017) that behavioral intentions were shaped by academic achievement and by perceived academic ability, in addition to attitudes and perceived social norms.

Table 5. Independent samples *t*-test results showing the differences in determining the behavioral intention of Webcon participants when analyzed by demographic Profile.

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	t-value	p-value	Decision on Ho
Webinar Attended	346	4.07	0.791	2.380	0.018*	Reject
Sex	154	3.89	0.851			
Male	192	0.891	0.162	0.162	0.871	Accept
Female	308	0.763				
Age	3	0.674				
Between						

	Groups			1.017	0.385	
	Within	496	0.662			Accept
	Groups					
	Total	499				
Civil Status	Between	2	0.032			
	Groups			.048	.953	
	Within	497	0.665			Accept
	Groups					
	Total	499				
Educational	Between	4	.240			
Attainment	Groups			.360	.837	
	Within	495	.666			Accept
	Groups					
	Total	499				

*p<0.05

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings, the following conclusion was drawn: Webcon participants manifested a high level of satisfaction in attending Webcon; Webcon participants manifested a high level of behavioral intention in attending Webcon; There is no significant difference in the level of satisfaction of Webcon participants when analyzed by Profile, except in terms of webinars attended; and there is no significant difference in the level of the behavioral intention of Webcon participants when analyzed by Profile, except in terms of Webinar attended.

The recommendations provided are based on the study's findings and conclusion: The attendees should always recommend the seminars and conventions they attended to other people so that they can likewise gain similar experiences and knowledge from the said event. Moreover, they should cherish their experiences during the events they attended, and they may share this with other people to encourage them to attend the same events. In addition, they should focus on the conducted webinars to gain important knowledge and information. Aside from this, they may also provide suggestions or recommendations to the facilitators of webinars to improve or enhance the overall activities.

To the Lecturer, they should encourage more people to attend seminars and conventions to gain knowledge and, at the same time, gain more experiences. They should also share their past experiences while still attending seminars and participants to encourage other people to do the same. In addition, they should continue to enhance or improve their skills and knowledge in imparting them to the participants. This can be done by doing extensive research and other studies. Moreover, they should also get regular feedback or comments from the participants to improve the conducted webinars, thus also attaining satisfaction.

Future Researchers may use or utilize the data and information from this study as reference and baseline data for future studies or research related to webinars and other online training or activities.

REFERENCES

- [1] Careless, J. (2012). Creating and presenting Great SEM Webinars. Accessed 20 Mar 2015. <http://rphelp.helmet.fi/ebSCO-w-b/ehost/detail/detail?sid=b0a88ac5-9d52-4d1e>
- [2] Davis, F. D. (2009). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 319-340.
- [3] Gremler, JP (2014). "Job characteristics and job satisfaction: understanding the role of enterprise resource planning system implementation," *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 34 No. 1, pp. 143-161.
- [4] Gegenfurtner, A. and Ebner, C. (2019), 'Webinars in higher education and professional training: a meta-analysis and systematic review of randomized controlled trials,' *Educational Research Review*, 28, 100293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2019.100293>.
- [5] Gegenfurtner, A., Zitt, A. and Ebner, C., 2020. Evaluating webinar-based training: a mixed methods study of trainee reactions toward digital web conferencing. *International Journal of Training and Development*, 24(1), pp.5

- [6] Huhmarkangas, S. (2014). Webinaareillasäästöä ja joustavuutta. Accessed 19 Mar 2015. <http://www.opentrainers.fi/blogi/item/2-webinaareilla-saastoa-ja-joustavuutta>
- [7] Kotler, P., Keller, K.L. (2019). *Marketing the Management*. 12 edition, Pearson Education Inc, Prentice-Hall.
- [8] Liao, H.L., & Lu, H.P. (2018). The role of experience and innovation characteristics in the adoption and continued use of e-learning websites. *Computers and Education*, 51(4), 1405-1416.
- [9] Lindblad, M. (2020). The Disadvantages of Webinars. Retrieved from <https://www.work.chron.com> > Careers > Computer Software Jobs
- [10] Malle, B.F. & Knobe J, (2017). "The folk concept of intentionality," *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, (33:2), pp. 101-121.
- [11] Mittal, Kumar, & Tsiros (2015). Understanding Customer Experience. *Harvard Business Review*. Retrieved from <http://hbr.org/2007/02/understanding-customer-experience/ar/1>
- [12] Newman, B. (2013). Best practices for training webinars. *Westchester County Business Journal*. May 8. 8
- [13] Olorunniwo, F. (2016). Service quality, customer satisfaction, and behavioral intentions in the service factory. *Journal of Service Marketing*, 20(1), 59-72.
- [14] Swan, P. & Combs, K. (2016). Management of multi-purpose stadiums: importance and performance measurement of service interfaces. *Int. J. Serv. Technol. Manag.* 14(2), 188-207 (2016)
- [15] Severt, W. (2017). User acceptance of computer technology: a comparison of two theoretical models. *Management Science*, 35(8), 982-1003.
- [16] Spiteri, J.M. & Dion, P.A. (2014). Customer value, overall satisfaction, end-user loyalty, and market performance in detail-intensive industries. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 33, 675-687.
- [17] Wu, C.H-J. & Liang, R.D. (2019). Effect of experiential value on customer satisfaction with service encounters in luxury-hotel restaurants. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 28, 586-593.